

ROLE OF ELECTROSPINNING PARAMETERS ON POLY(LACTIC-CO-GLYCOLIC ACID) AND POLY(CAPROLACTONE-CO-GLYCOLIC ACID) MEMBRANES

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Abstract

Poly(lactic-co-glycolic acid) (PLGA) and poly(caprolactone-co-glycolic acid) (PCLGA) solutions were electrospun into membranes with tailored fiber diameter of 1.8 μm . This particular fiber diameter was tuned depending on the used copolymer by adjusting the electrospinning parameters that mainly influence the fiber diameter. The greatest setting of the fiber diameter was achieved by varying the polymer solution variables (polymer concentration, solvents and solvents ratio).

PLGA was adequately electrospun with 1,1,1,3,3,3-hexafluoro-2-propanol (HFIP); whereas PCLGA required a polar solvent (such as chloroform) with lower dielectric constant. Moreover, due to the amorphous morphology of PCLGA, pyridine as salt had to be added to the starting solution to increase its conductivity and make it electrospinnable. To an accurate setting of fiber diameter, the voltage and the distance from needle to collector were varied.

Finally, the study of the surface tension, conductivity and viscosity of the polymer solutions allowed us to correlate these parameters with the electrospinning variables, so that prior knowledge of them enables predicting the required processing conditions.

Keywords: co-polymer; membrane; electrospinning; poly(lactic-co-glycolic acid); poly(caprolactone-co-glycolic acid); PLGA; PCLGA

1. INTRODUCTION

Electrospinning has been one of the most promising techniques in the tissue engineering and drug delivery fields for the last decades, due to the fact that electrospun nanofibers can mimic the physical structure of the native extracellular matrix (ECM). Also, it allows to obtain membranes with an extremely high surface-to-volume ratio and tunable porosity in a wide variety of sizes and shapes. [1]–[4]

Moreover, it is possible to control the properties of the nanofiber membranes (cell affinity, mechanical properties, biodegradability, etc) and their functionality (*i.e.*, degradation time) by means of two ways: (*i*) selecting the polymers and using co-polymers or polymer mixtures and (*ii*) making fibers with a specific fiber diameter. [5], [6]

Regarding the first way, biodegradable aliphatic polyesters, such as poly(lactic acid) (PLA), poly(glycolic acid) (PGA) and poly(caprolactone) (PCL), are widely used to obtain electrospun membranes. All of them, their copolymers and their blends have been approved by FDA for clinical use and are hydrolyzed into non-toxic natural metabolites, being eliminated from the body by the normal physiological processes. [7], [8]

Interestingly, the shortcomings of homopolymers can be overcome by their copolymerization. For example, PLA presents hydrophobicity, poor toughness and lack of reactive side chains, while PCL has a quite long degradation time and PGA degrades quickly in the aqueous medium due to its hydrophilicity.[9] Hence, poly(lactic-co-glycolic acid) (PLGA) has a faster biodegradability rate than PLA due to the presence of GA units, and poly(caprolactone-co-glycolic acid) (PCLGA) shows more elasticity than PLGA due to the effect of CL. [10], [11]

Notwithstanding the polymer choice, which will obviously influence the final properties of the electrospun membrane, the parameters of the polymer solutions and the

electrospinning process will also determine the fiber diameter and morphology. As we said previously, several properties of the membranes are related to the fiber diameter, so the understanding of the effect of those parameters is key to develop a specific material for a particular application.

The most important polymer solution parameters involved in the fiber diameter are the surface tension, the viscosity and the conductivity. [11], [12] The effect of the density solution has not been studied much yet because of its relationship with other parameters. [13]

Due to the fact that electrospinning uses an electric potential to overcome the surface tension, a reduced surface tension favors the formation of fibers without beads. This parameter is strongly influenced by the nature of the solvent. [14], [15] The viscosity is related to the opposition of the jet to be ejected. A too low viscosity may result in the interruption of polymeric filaments and droplets of polymer, while a too high viscosity makes it impossible to extrude the polymer. Nevertheless, increasing the viscosity, the diameter of the fiber also increases. [15]–[17] Finally, an increase in the conductivity of the polymer solution entails a decrease in fiber diameter.[18]

When the electrospinnability of a solution is low, the addition of a salt like pyridine has shown to improve it, because it increases the conductivity of the polymer solution. The advantage of using pyridine in electrospinning is that it is not necessary to remove it after the process because it evaporates during the solution fly between the needle and the collector. [18], [19]

The main purpose of this study was, thus, to obtain the electrospinning conditions of PLGA and PCLGA copolymers to achieve fiber membranes thereof with approximately 1.8 μm fiber diameter. We chose this fiber diameter as goal to allow comparison with the

procedure set in a previous work for membranes of PLA, PCL and PLA/PCL mixtures. Membranes with this diameter were found to show the most effective configuration for BSA release compared to thinner fibers.[20] Co-polymer solutions were here characterized by determination of their density, surface tension, viscosity and conductivity to relate with the parameters of the electrospinning process, specially voltage and distance from needle to collector.

2. MATERIALS AND METHODS

2.1. Polymeric solutions

Poly (lactic-co-glycolic acid) (PLGA)—as a mixture of PLGA acid terminated (50:50, M_w 38000-54000, *Sigma Aldrich*) and PLGA ester terminated (50:50, M_w 38000-54000, *Sigma Aldrich*) at 50% w/w—, and poly (caprolactone-co-glycolic acid) (PCLGA; caprolactone:glycolic 45:55, viscosity 1.5 dL/g, *Sigma Aldrich*) were solved in chloroform (chlor; stabilized with ethanol, *Scharlab*) and 1,1,1,3,3,3-hexafluoro-2-propanol (HFIP; ≥ 99%, *Sigma Aldrich*) at different concentrations (from 10 to 25% w/v). The lower electrospinnability of PCLGA was dealt by adding 20% v/v of pyridine (pyr; anhydrous, 99.8%, *Sigma Aldrich*) to the solution. Once the solutions were prepared, they were stirred during 48h before electrospinning.

2.2. Electrospinning

A syringe with a needle (24 G, 0.31 mm inner diameter) was filled with the polymeric solution and introduced in a syringe pump (RS-232, model NE 1000. *New Era Pump Systems, Inc.*) to eject the solution at 2 ml/h. The collector was covered with an aluminum foil and placed at different distances (from 13 to 20 cm). A voltage source (OL400W-503, *HiTek Power*) was used to apply a difference of voltage from 13 to 20 kV between

the needle and the collector. The process was carried out in a home-made chamber where a dry forced air flow was circulated to maintain the humidity below 20% and to remove solvent vapors.

Once electrospun, the membranes were placed overnight in a fume hood to ensure the complete evaporation of solvents. After that, the membranes were separated from the aluminum foil and stored in a fridge (4°C) until characterization.

2.3. Scanning electron microscopy (SEM)

To determine the electrospinning parameters that result in membranes of 1.8 µm without defects, such as beads, the membranes were first observed in a scanning electron microscope (JEOL model JSM6300) with a working distance of 12 mm and a voltage of 15 kV. The samples were previously sputtered with gold to make them conductive.

When the SEM images showed an adequate fiber membrane structure without defects, the fiber diameters were assessed using the ImageJ software, by measuring the diameter of 100 fibers from two SEM images per material, at a magnification of ×1000.

2.4. Characterization of the polymeric solutions

Density

A pycnometer of 10 ml was used to calculate the density of the polymeric solutions. The volume was calibrated with distilled water as reference liquid, which density could be estimated by the following formula [21]:

$$\rho_w = 999.85308 + 6.32693 \cdot 10^{-2}T - 8.523829 \cdot 10^{-3}T^2 + 6.943248 \cdot 10^{-5}T^3 - 3.821216 \cdot 10^{-7}T^4 \quad \text{kg/m}^3$$

where T is the temperature in Celsius degrees.

Weighing the mass of the empty pycnometer (m_p), the pycnometer filled with distilled water (m_{p+w}) and the pycnometer filled with the polymeric solution (m_{p+s}), the density of the polymeric solution (ρ_s) was obtained as:

$$\rho_s = \frac{m_{p+s} - m_p}{m_{p+w} - m_p} \cdot \rho_w$$

Three measurements of each type of solution were done.

Surface tension

The polymeric solutions have a high viscosity and their solvents are highly volatile so the surface tension of them was determined with the modified Tate's law, as described in a previous work. Briefly, five drops were weighed using an airtight device to reduce the effect of solvent evaporation. After that, by means of the density of the solutions and applying Tate's law, the surface tension of the polymeric solution was obtained. [20]

Viscosity

To measure the dynamic viscosity of the polymer solutions, an oscillatory assay was performed in a parallel plate's rheometer (Discovery HR-2 hybrid rheometer, TA Instruments) at angular frequency of 100 rad/s. 500 μ l of polymer solution was measured each time, 3 replicates per composition.

The complex viscosity (η^*) was obtained from the data of the complex modulus (G^*) and the angular frequency (ω) as:

$$\eta^* = \frac{G^*}{\omega}$$

Conductivity

The conductivity of the polymeric solutions was measured per triplicate with a conductivity meter (Crison EC-Meter Basic 30+). The instrument was previously calibrated with three standard solutions whose conductivity was known.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1. Determination of the electrospinning parameters for PLGA and PCLGA

According to a previous work, the main effective parameters to modify fiber diameter are the polymer concentration and the solvent, because they are highly related to viscosity. [20] After that, voltage plays also an important role in fiber diameter. So firstly, the mentioned solution parameters were analyzed and next the fiber diameter was set by modifying the voltage. When a more accurate setting was necessary, it was achieved with the modification of the distance from needle to collector and the flow rate.

Considering the results of [22], [23], the starting parameters for both copolymers were established as: a concentration of 10% (w/v) in HFIP with a flow rate of 2 ml/h, 17 kV and 13 cm. The SEM results are shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1. SEM images of PLGA and PCLGA electrospun membranes at 10% wt/v in HFIP, 2 ml/h, 17 kV and 13 cm. Scale bar: 60 μ m.

PLGA was adequately electrospun although it presents beads. Nevertheless, PCLGA image shows that fibers were not properly formed, probably because the solvent was not evaporated during the electrospinning process.

Due to the different behavior of both copolymers in the electrospinning, each copolymer was treated by a specific way: (i) for PLGA, the initial SEM images showed that an increment in polymer concentration was necessary. For that reason, the concentration was increased up to 25% w/v maintaining HFIP as a solvent. In this way, it was expected that beads disappeared and the fiber diameter increased [15], [24]; (ii) for PCLGA, the use of chloroform as solvent was proposed because of its polarity and its lower dielectric constant. [25], [26] Moreover, the concentration was also increased up to 20% w/v.

The electrospinning process parameters were maintained constant to evaluate only the effect of the polymer solutions parameters.

Figure 2. SEM images of PLGA (10 and 25 %w/v in HFIP) and PCLGA (18 and 20 % w/v in chloroform) at 2 ml/h, 15 kV and 13 cm. Scale bar: 60 µm.

As Figure 2 shows, the increment on the polymer concentration for PLGA allowed obtaining homogeneous membranes without defects. Moreover, the diameter analysis determined that the average of the fiber diameter was 1.62 µm, thus polymer solution parameters were established in 25% w/v in HFIP.

The use of chloroform with a higher polymer concentration of PCLGA entails the feasibility of electrospinning this co-polymer, although the fibers were not formed adequately. It is well known that a way to obtain uniform and thinner fibers is to increase the conductivity of the polymer solution. Therefore, to achieve finer and uniform fiber diameters, salts can be added to the solution to increase its conductivity.[18], [27], [28]

Thus, pyridine at 5% and 10% v/v concentration was added to the solution of 20% PCLGA in chloroform, and these polymer solutions were electrospun maintaining the rest of electrospinning parameters in 2 ml/h, 15 kV and 13 cm.

Figure 3. SEM images of 20%w/v PCLGA in chloroform with 5% and 10%v/v of pyridine. 2 ml/h, 15 kV and 20 cm. Scale bar: 10 μm.

By adding pyridine in the solution at those concentrations, the fibers were much more defined, although the diameter is higher than the required one because of the high concentration of the polymer solution. Therefore, in order to obtain 1.8 microns fibers, the concentration of the polymer solutions was varied from 20 to 17% w/v. Moreover, chloroform:pyridine (80:20) was used as a solvent system to improve the effect of pyridine in the process.

Once the polymer solution parameters were established, the electrospinning process parameters were modified to an accurate setting of the diameter. Figure 4 shows the effect of voltage in PLGA membranes, at 2 ml/h and 13 cm.

Figure 4. SEM images and histograms of the fiber diameter for 25% w/v PLGA in HFIP at 13, 15 and 17 kV by maintaining flow rate = 2 ml/h and distance from-needle-to-collector = 13 cm. Scale bar: 60 μm .

The fiber diameter first increased with the applied voltage, and next it decreased after getting a maximum at an intermediate voltage around 15 kV (1.51 μm -average diameter – 13 kV, 1.76 μm – 15 kV and 1.62 μm – 17 kV). This non-monotonic effect of the voltage on the fiber diameter has previously been observed for different materials. [29]–[31] Besides, it was also observed that the higher the voltage the higher variability in fiber diameter (standard deviation: 0.14 μm – 13 kV, 0.20 μm – 15 kV and 0.26 μm – 17 kV).

To sum up, the electrospinning process parameters for PLGA were established as 2 ml/h, 15 kV and 13 cm.

The effect of voltage on PCLGA membranes (Figure 5) was studied by modifying the distance from 13 cm to 20 cm, to reduce the fiber diameter in order to achieve a greater elongation of fibers.

Figure 5. SEM images and histograms of the fiber diameter for 17% w/v PCLGA in chloroform:pyridine (80:20) at 15 kV and 20 kV by maintaining flow rate = 2 ml/h and distance from-needle-to-collector = 20 cm. Scale bar: 10 μm .

As it occurred with PLGA, the diameter of electrospun fibers increases at higher voltages ($1.15 \pm 0.21 \mu\text{m}$ – 15 kV and $1.74 \pm 0.28 \mu\text{m}$ – 20 kV). According to these results, the electrospinning conditions of PCLGA to obtain homogeneous fibers of approximately 1.8 μm were: 17% PCLGA in chloroform:pyridine (80:20), 2 ml/h, 20 kV and 20 cm.

In Table 1 the electrospinning conditions for both polymers are summarized, together with the fiber diameter obtained, much closed to the objective of 1.8 μm (1.76 μm for PLGA and 1.74 μm for PCLGA).

Table 1. Electrospinning parameters of PLGA and PCLGA to obtain membranes of 1.8 μm .

	PLGA	PCLGA
Fiber diameter (μm)	1.76 ± 0.20	1.74 ± 0.28
Polymer concentration (% w/v)	25	17
Solvent	HFIP	Chloroform:pyridine (80:20)
Flow rate (ml/h)	2	2
Voltage (kV)	15	20

<i>Distance needle to collector (cm)</i>	13	20
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3.2. Characterization of the solution parameters: density, surface tension, viscosity and conductivity

The polymer solutions of Table 1 were next characterized in terms of density, surface tension, viscosity and conductivity. The densities were 1.268 ± 0.010 g/ml for that of PLGA and 1.018 ± 0.006 g/ml for PCLGA. This difference can be attributed on the one hand to the higher concentration of the PLGA solution, which increases its density. On the other hand, HFIP has a higher density than chloroform and pyridine, and therefore their mixture.

In general, density has a moderate influence on fiber diameter and there are very few studies assessing its effect on fiber morphology. In an electrospinning theoretical model [13], as well as in [32], it was found that the increase of the density implies a slight decrease of the fiber diameter. For that reason, the applied voltage and distance from-needle-to-collector of PCLGA solution are higher than PLGA.

Co-polymer solutions of Table 1 showed the following surface tensions: 158.2 ± 0.5 mN/m for PLGA and 136.8 ± 0.9 mN/m for PCLGA. The higher surface tension of the PLGA solution results in a slightly greater opposition of this solution to be ejected. For this reason, the solvent could evaporate faster and the distance from-needle-to-collector can be reduced from 20 cm for PCLGA to 13 cm for PLGA.

The values of storage (G') and loss (G'') moduli, $\tan(\delta)$, dynamic (η') and storage (η'') viscosities are shown in Table 2.

Table 2. Storage (G') and loss (G'') moduli, $\tan(\delta)$, dynamic (η') and storage (η'') viscosities for PLGA and PCLGA solutions in Table 1, measured at 100 rad/s.

	PLGA	PCLGA
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G' (Pa)	901.5 ± 1.6	1180 ± 90.4
G'' (Pa)	259.5 ± 6.5	232.4 ± 25.8
$\tan(\delta)$	0.288 ± 0.008	0.197 ± 0.020
η' (Pa·s)	2.595 ± 0.065	2.324 ± 0.258
η'' (Pa·s)	9.015 ± 0.016	11.798 ± 0.904

The storage modulus (G') represents the energy stored in the elastic structure of the sample, whereas the loss modulus (G'') represents the viscous part of the amount of energy dissipated thereof. [33] Therefore, plasticity is related to the loss modulus and elasticity to the storage modulus. Plasticity contributes to nanofiber formation and the elasticity is critical in the stage of jet formation and appropriate elongation, preventing the jet from breaking up. A higher G' results consequently in a beadless nanofiber structure. [34] In this case, both co-polymer solutions show a higher storage modulus with respect than the loss one, being it greater for PCLGA.

Nevertheless, the dynamic viscosity (η') of PLGA is higher than PCLGA. This is probably due to the addition of pyridine, which has been found to decrease the dynamic viscosity. [35] A higher dynamic viscosity entails a more uniform distribution of the nanofibers, as can be observed in Table 1 for PLGA. Nonetheless, it seems there is no linear relationship between fiber diameter and dynamic viscosity. [36]

As for their conductivity, the PLGA solution yielded a value of 0.98 S/cm, whereas that of PCLGA is 0.31 S/cm. This latter lower conductivity explains the need of a higher voltage for the PCLGA solution to make it electrospinnable. The features of the polymeric solutions of Table 1 are summarized in Table 3.

Table 3. Summary of properties of the polymeric solutions listed in Table 1.

	PLGA	PCLGA
Density (g/ml)	1.268 ± 0.010	1.018 ± 0.006
Surface tension (mN/m)	158.2 ± 0.5	136.8 ± 0.9

<i>Conductivity (S/cm)</i>	0.98 ± 0.01	0.31 ± 0.01
<i>Dynamic viscosity (Pa·s)</i>	2.60 ± 0.065	2.32 ± 0.256

4. CONCLUSIONS

Membranes of PLGA and PCLGA were successfully obtained with comparable fiber diameters of approximately 1.8 μm . PLGA is adequately electrospun in HFIP, although a high polymer concentration (25 % w/v) is necessary to avoid the presence of beads; nevertheless, the polymer/solvent system of PCLGA/HFIP is not electrospinnable, probably due to the polarity of the solvent. For that reason, for PCLGA the use of chloroform as solvent is more appropriate to obtain electrospun membranes, being also necessary the addition of salt (like pyridine).

To a finer setting of the fiber diameter, the electrospinning process parameters had to be modified, especially voltage and distance from-needle-to-collector. These parameters are related to the polymer solution properties, such as surface tension, viscosity and conductivity.

Indeed, the higher surface tension of the PLGA solution allows reducing the distance between the needle and the collector, because it hinders the ejection of the solution and, consequently, the evaporation of the solvent occurs more easily. On the contrary, the low conductivity of PCLGA requires the increment of the voltage.

All in all, these findings indicate that the properties of the polymer solutions play a main role on the morphology of their membranes. Advantage of knowing them can be taken to tune other electrospinning parameters such as voltage and distance to collector, in order to obtain membranes with a specific fiber diameter.

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